

A Study on Food Safety and Hygiene Behavioral Attitudes in University Practice Kitchens

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the attitudes and behaviors of students receiving training in university practice kitchens regarding food safety and hygiene practices. A quantitative research design was employed, utilizing a survey questionnaire as the data collection instrument. The surveys were administered to culinary program students at foundation universities in Istanbul. Ethical approval was obtained from the university's ethics committee in 2022. The participants' levels of awareness, attitudes and behavioral tendencies concerning hygiene practices were analyzed. The collected data provide insight into the current state of hygiene education in practice kitchens and help identify areas for improvement. The study seeks to contribute to the development of educational programs aimed at enhancing food safety awareness. As a result of the research, it was determined that students generally exhibit positive attitudes toward food safety and hygiene. When the findings of the study were analyzed in relation to demographic variables, it was concluded that attitudes toward food safety significantly differed based on age and gender. In particular, it was found that awareness of food safety was higher among younger individuals. Additionally, male students were observed to display more positive attitudes on this issue compared to female students. When attitudes toward hygiene behavior were examined in relation to demographic characteristics and type of high school attended, it was found that age and gender did not lead to significant differences. However, a statistically significant difference was identified based on the type of high school. Accordingly, students without a vocational high school background exhibited higher levels of hygiene-related attitudes, whereas those who graduated from vocational high schools were found to have lower levels of hygiene behavior attitudes.

Keywords: Food safety, Hygiene, Behavioral attitude, Practice kitchens

INTRODUCTION

Food safety and hygiene are two fundamental elements that play a key role in protecting human health. These two concepts not only influence individual health conditions but also directly impact public health, economic production capacity, labor efficiency, and the sustainability of food systems (WHO, 2006; DPT, 2006). The consumption of unsafe food may result in individual health issues, impose additional financial burdens on national healthcare systems, and lead to labor force losses. Furthermore, it can undermine trust in international trade and pose threats to economic relations. According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, millions of people around the world suffer from health problems due to unsafe food consumption each year. In developing countries, more than one-third of the population is affected by foodborne illnesses (Sani & Siow, 2014). For instance, in the United States, approximately 76 million cases of foodborne poisoning are reported annually, 325,000 of which require hospitalization, and around 5,000 result in death (Yarrow, 2006). In this context, food safety is regarded not only as a component of health policies but also as a key element of economic development.

There are numerous factors that threaten food safety. These include environmental pollution, population growth, global climate change, intensive use of chemicals in agricultural production, changes in consumer habits, low levels of education and income, inadequate infrastructure, and legislative or inspection gaps (Uzunöz et al., 2008). Particularly at every stage of the food production chain from raw material supply to the final delivery to the consumer violations of hygiene rules lead to an increase in risks in a comprehensive and systematic manner. Accordingly, the production of safe food is not solely dependent on the adequacy of technical infrastructure, but is also directly associated with the knowledge levels, awareness, and attitudes of the individuals involved in the process (Bucak, 2012). Based on this, it can be stated that if

the human factor is neglected, even the most advanced technological systems may prove insufficient.

Hygiene can be defined as a holistic system that includes physical precautions and behavioral approaches aimed at maintaining a healthy life (Erdem, 2014). Within this framework, the concept of sanitation, which is considered a complementary element of hygiene, includes cleaning and sterilization practices aimed at minimizing environmental risks (Arat & Şimşek, 2014). Foodborne illnesses generally originate from three main groups of risk factors: biological (e.g., Salmonella, E. coli), chemical (e.g., pesticide residues, cleaning agents), and physical (e.g., glass or metal fragments, foreign objects) (Bucak, 2012). Effective management of these risks is only possible through structured training programs, a consistent inspection mechanism, and high levels of awareness.

When reviewing the relevant literature, it becomes evident that individuals employed in the food sector possess a certain level of knowledge regarding hygiene and sanitation, yet there are significant deficiencies in transforming this knowledge into behavior (Demirel, 2009; Erdem, 2014; Şimşek, 2014). This indicates that training on hygiene and sanitation should be planned not only at the institutional level but also from a behavioral perspective. In particular, it is important to assess the extent to which students enrolled in vocational education programs such as culinary or gastronomy departments reflect their knowledge of hygiene and food safety in their attitudes and behaviors (Aratoğlu, 2015). Furthermore, the recent COVID-19 pandemic has turned hygiene into not just a health issue, but also an area of social responsibility. Although public awareness of hygiene practices has increased during this period, the sustainability of such behaviors depends on the quality of educational policies and the effectiveness of hands-on teaching practices (Özçakmak & Var, 2020).

The primary aim of this study is to examine the knowledge levels of students receiving education in university training kitchens regarding hygiene and food safety, and to

reveal how this knowledge is reflected in their behavioral attitudes. The study also seeks to identify potential mismatches between knowledge and behavior and develop structural improvement suggestions for educational processes. While possessing knowledge is essential for maintaining effective hygiene practices, it is not considered sufficient on its own. Within this context, university training kitchens are regarded not only as laboratory environments where technical skills are acquired, but also as strategic learning spaces where students build their professional identities, internalize a culture of hygiene, and develop ethical awareness related to food safety. The experiences gained in these environments play a crucial role in the students' transition to the industry and contribute to the development of professional attitudes that reflect both theoretical knowledge and professional behavior. However, in order to ensure this transformation, training kitchens must be supported not only in terms of physical infrastructure but also with pedagogical, behavioral, and supervisory components. Making students' behavioral patterns regarding hygiene and food safety observable during the practice process transforms these environments into significant feedback mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating educational outcomes. Therefore, behavior-based evaluation studies conducted in training kitchens serve as a guiding tool for both educators and industry stakeholders.

Strengthening behavioral attitudes related to food safety contributes to the development of students' individual awareness and social responsibility, supporting the adoption of an ethics-based professional approach. In this regard, the study aims not only to identify the current state of individual hygiene habits but also to examine how these habits can evolve into an institutional culture through education. Thus, the outcomes of vocational education can be assessed from a more holistic perspective, and the contribution of universities' practical training processes will not be limited to technical competencies but will also foster behavioral norms that prioritize public health.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Food Safety and Hygiene Behavioral Attitudes in Kitchens

The issue of hygiene and food safety in kitchens is significant not only for individual health but also for the sustainability of public health. Business efficiency, customer satisfaction, and social welfare are directly related to these concepts. In particular, the knowledge level, attitudes, and behaviors of individuals working in the food and beverage sector play a critical role in ensuring food safety in kitchens. Parlak (2020) categorizes hygiene practices in the food sector and food production under three main headings: "Personal Hygiene," "Food Hygiene and Sanitation (Food Safety)," and "Occupational Hygiene (Industrial Hygiene)." According to Aydoğan & Erol (2023), foodborne illnesses arise due to factors such as insufficient personal hygiene and sanitation, cross-contamination, improper cooking in terms of required temperature and time, inappropriate temperature and humidity conditions during storage, and the failure to select reliable suppliers during procurement.

Hygiene, in its simplest definition, encompasses the measures taken to protect against disease-causing agents and harmful microorganisms in order to maintain a healthy life (Erdem, 2014). In this sense, it not only involves physical cleanliness but also represents a holistic approach to preventing contagious diseases and ensuring the protection and continuity of health (Hossain, 2012; Nurudeen & Toyin, 2020). Personal hygiene refers to the individual care required to maintain a healthy life. Neglecting personal hygiene may lead to the contamination of food through various factors such as hands, mouth and nose, hair and skin, uniforms, and personal equipment (Özmen-Arısoy, İnce & Olcay, 2021). Therefore, contamination caused by staff especially in foods that have not been heat-treated should be taken into account. Pathogenic elements may be transferred from raw to final food products through staff members, equipment, or tools used during food preparation (Güzel & Ertaş Onmaz, 2022). Food service personnel must maintain personal hygiene in order to protect consumers from foodborne illnesses.

It is crucial for managers to be aware of this issue and for hygiene training to be provided to personnel at regular intervals to address any knowledge gaps and ensure compliance with hygiene rules (Kemer & Etyemez, 2020).

Proper storage, production, and presentation of food ingredients at appropriate temperatures and for appropriate durations are of critical importance in preventing foodborne illnesses. The temperature range of 5°C to 60°C is considered a “danger zone” as it is optimal for microbial growth, with the most rapid growth occurring between 16°C and 50°C. Foodborne illnesses often result from leaving food at room temperature for more than 2 to 4 hours. Therefore, ensuring that food is cooked and cooled at the required temperatures is vital (Sevim & Görkem, 2016). Cold ready-to-serve foods should be kept below 10°C, and hot foods should be held above 65°C, for example using the bain-marie method (Yüksel-Bilsel, 2024).

Food hygiene refers to the safe handling and processing of food from production to final consumption without contamination, in a way that does not harm human health (Aratoğlu, 2015; Aksu, 2000). Food safety, on the other hand, is a multidimensional process that aims to eliminate biological, chemical, and physical hazards from food products offered to consumers so that they do not pose health risks (WHO, 2006). In this context, food safety is considered a responsibility that must be fulfilled at all stages of the food supply chain. Food safety is not limited to individual practices; it also requires institutional inspection systems, regulatory frameworks, and staff training to function together. In Turkey, the term “gıda güvenilirliği” (food reliability) is often used interchangeably with “gıda güvenliği” (food safety), both corresponding to the concept of “food safety” in English. However, this term should not be confused with “food security,” which refers to individuals’ sustainable access to sufficient, healthy, and nutritious food (FAO, 2000; DPT, 2006). The main goal of food sanitation is to eliminate physical, chemical, and biological contaminants in food in order to protect consumer health. Accordingly, effective hygiene and sanitation management plays a crucial role in maintaining the sustainability

of both reliable food production and public health (Erdem, 2014; Aratoğlu, 2015).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, hygiene-related behaviors and attitudes came into the global spotlight. Practices such as handwashing, surface disinfection, and maintaining physical distance were widely adopted as effective public health strategies (Özçakmak & Var, 2020; WHO, 2020). In this period, hygiene precautions transformed from being solely personal behaviors to a matter of public health responsibility. Especially in environments with frequent contact, such as kitchens, compliance with hygiene rules plays a vital role in preventing the spread of infectious diseases (Çiçek et al., 2020; Nicolle, 2007). A review of academic studies on hygiene behaviors reveals a strong focus on the healthcare sector, while research conducted in educational institutions remains limited (Yağmur, 2007; Gül & Özey, 2020). However, schools and vocational education institutions serve as important social interaction settings for instilling food safety and hygiene awareness in individuals (Ormancı et al., 2012; Deb et al., 2010). In this regard, vocational training processes should be structured not only to impart technical knowledge and skills but also to develop health-related attitudes and behaviors. Raising awareness among students about hygiene and food safety from an early age is a fundamental condition for the continuation of healthy practices in their professional lives.

In conclusion, awareness regarding food safety and hygiene must be recognized not only as an individual concern but also as an institutional responsibility. Studies on behavioral attitudes toward food safety and hygiene in kitchens have shown that even individuals with high levels of knowledge may face challenges in practical application. This reality necessitates a comprehensive restructuring of educational content that integrates both theoretical and practical dimensions. The adoption and long-term retention of hygiene-related behaviors among individuals depend not only on personal effort but also on the presence of a continuous and holistic system of education and supervision.

METHODOLOGY

In the study, the phenomenological The primary The primary aim of this study is to assess the food safety and hygiene behavioral attitudes of students studying in university training kitchens and to analyze whether these attitudes significantly differ according to demographic variables. Training kitchens are critical environments in which students develop their professional knowledge and skills. The food safety and hygiene behaviors exhibited in these settings are of great importance for both individual health and professional competence. In this regard, the study focuses on measuring students' attitudes toward hygiene and safety and analyzing these attitudes based on demographic characteristics such as age, gender, and type of high school education.

A quantitative research approach was adopted, and the data collection process was structured within the framework of the descriptive survey model. For the development of the measurement instruments, existing tools validated and verified in the literature were utilized. The scale developed by Ghezzi and Ayoun (2013) adapted to training kitchen conditions to assess food safety. To measure hygiene behavioral attitudes, the scale developed based on the study by Ayaz and Aydın (2018) was employed. Both scales were adapted to suit the specific context of the study, and necessary revisions were made based on expert academic opinions.

The scale translations were checked by academics with expertise in English. The translated survey was checked by three different academics with expertise in gastronomy and tourism. Any unclear expressions or other sentence errors were checked, and implementation was decided.

The questionnaire consists of three main sections. The first section evaluates participants' attitudes toward food safety, the second section addresses their hygiene behavior attitudes, and the third section contains questions regarding demographic characteristics such as age, gender, and type of high school education. All items in the scales were structured in a five-point Likert format, ranging from 1 (Strongly

disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree).

The population of the study comprises students enrolled in culinary and tourism programs at universities. The sample includes a total of 261 students studying in training kitchens at a university in Turkey in 2022 who voluntarily participated in the research. Taking into account the limited size of the population, the sample of this study is considered statistically adequate at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error (Cochran, 1977). Ethical approval was obtained in 2022 under the number E-42435178-050.06.04-26776.

First, descriptive analyses were conducted on the collected data. Then, to test whether students' food safety and hygiene attitudes differed significantly according to demographic variables, independent samples t-tests and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were applied. All statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS software, and significance levels were interpreted and reported accordingly.

Normality, Reliability, and Validity Analyses

To determine whether the data collected to measure food safety and hygiene behavioral attitudes in university training kitchens followed a normal distribution, descriptive statistics were analyzed. For the food safety scale, the following values were calculated: mean (Mean = 3.8602), median (Median = 4.2222), skewness (Skewness = -1.031), and kurtosis (Kurtosis = -0.452). The proximity of the mean and median values and the skewness and kurtosis values falling within the ± 1.5 range indicate that the data obtained from the food safety scale are normally distributed (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019).

Similarly, for the hygiene behavior attitude scale, the calculated values were: mean (Mean = 3.8042), median (Median = 4.0625), skewness (Skewness = -0.876), and kurtosis (Kurtosis = -0.593). These values also fall within the acceptable range, supporting the normality of the dataset.

Based on the descriptive statistics findings for both scales, it was concluded that the datasets met the assumption of normal distribution. Therefore, it was deemed appropriate to use

parametric test methods in the relational (difference) analyses.

To evaluate the reliability of the scales used in the study, Cronbach's Alpha coefficients were examined. Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.70 indicate internal consistency and, therefore, the reliability of the scales (Büyüköztürk, 2013; **Table 1. Reliability Analysis Results of the Scales**

<i>Reliability Analysis of the Food Safety Scale in University Training Kitchens</i>	
Cronbach's Alpha	Items
.967	27
<i>Reliability Analysis of the Hygiene Behavior Attitude Scale in University Training Kitchens</i>	
Cronbach's Alpha	Items
.931	16

The results of the reliability analysis indicate that both scales used in this study demonstrate a high level of internal consistency. The Food Safety Scale, which includes 27 items, yielded a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.967, while the Hygiene Behavior Attitude Scale, consisting of 16 items, produced a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.931. These values exceed the generally accepted threshold of 0.70 (Büyüköztürk, 2013; Nunnally, 1978), confirming that both instruments are highly reliable and suitable for further statistical analysis. In order to enhance the interpretability and meaningfulness of the dataset, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was also conducted. The results revealed that while the majority of item loadings

Nunnally, 1978). The analyses revealed that all scales used in this study had Cronbach's Alpha values above the threshold. These results indicate that the scales exhibit a high level of internal consistency and reliably measure the intended constructs. The relevant findings are presented in detail in 'Table 1'.

remained consistent with the original scale structures, certain deviations were observed. These deviations may stem from variations in participants' perception frameworks and could also be influenced by cultural or contextual factors specific to the study setting. Additionally, the eigenvalues and explained variance ratios were examined to evaluate the strength of the factor structures. The results demonstrated that the total variance explained by the extracted factors was considerably high, indicating that the factor structures of both scales are robust and conceptually sound. Further details regarding the results of the factor analysis are presented in 'Table 2'.

Table 2. Reliability Analysis Results of the Scales

<i>Food Safety Scale in University Training Kitchens Items</i>	<i>Factor Loadings</i>
Food is properly protected during transportation outside the kitchen.	.608
The temperature of the cold storage area for food ingredients is visible.	.828
Monitoring food temperature can prevent foodborne illnesses.	.796
Chafing dishes are properly lit and functional before placing food in them.	.814
Food is always placed on ice to maintain proper temperature.	.684
Backup items used for buffets are labeled and properly sealed in the kitchen storage.	.778
Food that has been left out for a long time is removed from the kitchen.	.758
Food in chafing dishes is checked and illuminated.	.840
Hot food is always cooked and maintained at the proper temperature.	.849
Storage temperatures of ingredients can be monitored.	.833
Chafing dishes are cleaned after each use.	.830
Attention is paid to avoid wear and chipping on tableware.	.799
Chafing dishes are checked before being offered for use.	.804
Kitchen equipment is cleaned.	.831
The temperatures of hot-holding materials are checked.	.884
No handwashing station is available.	.763

Table 2. Reliability Analysis Results of the Scales (continued)

<i>Food Safety Scale in University Training Kitchens Items</i>	<i>Factor Loadings</i>
Hands are washed after every meal service.	.789
Reminders are given to wash hands before serving after washing dishes.	.745
Water temperature is sufficient for handwashing.	.789
Handwashing units are available for operations conducted outside the kitchen.	.776
We do not start work in dirty uniforms that would compromise food safety.	.642
We tend to eat or drink during kitchen operations.	.701
Disposable clean gloves are always worn while preparing food.	.816
Hands can be dried on clothing.	.719
Wearing jewelry is allowed.	.806
We wash our hands after taking a break.	.768
We wash our hands after touching our hair or face.	.798
Kaiser- Mayer- Olkin: .971; Total Variance Explained: % 66.491	
<i>Hygiene Behavior Attitude Scale in University Training Kitchens Items</i>	<i>Factor Loadings</i>
I know the required temperature level in cold storage.	.846
I know the required temperature level in dry storage.	.831
I know which foods are most susceptible to microbial contamination.	.779
I know how long ready-to-serve food can be stored in a refrigerator.	.813
I know how frequently cutting boards should be cleaned.	.791
I believe different counters should be used to prevent cross-contamination.	.812
I care about cleaning utensils (ladles, strainers, spoons, etc.) that fall on the ground.	.787
I care about washing my hands after using the restroom in the kitchen.	.833
I care about washing my hands before starting work in the kitchen.	.842
I care about wearing an apron while working in the kitchen.	.770
I care about wearing a hairnet while working in the kitchen.	.769
I care about wearing a mask while working in the kitchen.	.598
I believe cracked or broken plates and glasses can be used in service.	.772
I believe chewing gum is acceptable while preparing food.	.799
I believe it is acceptable to touch cooked and ready-to-serve food with bare hands.	.764
I believe one can attend school while having the flu or similar illnesses.	.758
Kaiser- Mayer- Olkin: .950; Total Variance Explained: % 72.077	

To evaluate dataset suitability for factor analysis, we performed KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. KMO coefficients were 0.971 (Food Safety Scale) and 0.950 (Hygiene Behavior Attitude Scale). According to Kaiser (1974), these "marvelous" values (≥ 0.90) indicate high sample suitability. Bartlett's Test was statistically significant for both scales ($p < 0.001$), confirming sufficient variable correlations. As Hair et al. (2014) note, significant Bartlett's results validate data appropriateness for multivariate analysis. The high explained variance demonstrates strong factor structures and confirms construct validity. These results establish robust statistical foundations for scientifically reliable interpretations.

Data Analysis and Research Findings

This section presents results from descriptive and inferential analyses of students' food safety and hygiene attitudes in university training kitchens. The study examined whether these perceptions differ by demographics (age, gender, high school background) using descriptive statistics, t-tests, and ANOVA. We analyzed mean scores, frequencies, and standard deviations, then tested for significant differences across demographic groups. This approach identified which groups showed more positive or negative attitudes, providing insights for educational policy. From these analyses, we developed a research model with hypotheses to test significant differences and relationships, which will be presented in the following section.

Figure 1. Research Model

H1: Students' levels of food safety and hygiene behavior attitudes are positively oriented. (Explanation: This hypothesis aims to test students' general attitude levels based on the mean scores of the scales, assuming 3.00 as the neutral value on the Likert scale. Mean scores above 3.00 indicate a positive and favorable attitude.)

H2 (Main Hypothesis for Food Safety Attitude): Students' food safety attitudes differ significantly according to their demographic characteristics.

- H2a: Students' food safety attitudes differ significantly by age.
- H2b: Students' food safety attitudes differ significantly by gender.

- H2c: Students' food safety attitudes differ significantly by type of high school education.

H3 (Main Hypothesis for Hygiene Behavior Attitude): Students' hygiene behavior attitudes differ significantly according to their demographic characteristics.

- H3a: Students' hygiene behavior attitudes differ significantly by age.
- H3b: Students' hygiene behavior attitudes differ significantly by gender.
- H3c: Students' hygiene behavior attitudes differ significantly by type of high school education.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Participants' Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage
Age	18–24 years	120	46.0
	25–34 years	106	40.6
	35–44 years	35	13.4
	Total	261	100.0
Gender	Male	93	35.6
	Female	168	64.4
	Total	261	100.0
Type of High School Education	Graduate of a high school offering Culinary or Tourism education	94	36.0
	Graduate of a different type of high school	167	64.0
	Total	261	100.0

The sample of the study consists of a total of 261 students receiving education in university training kitchens. An examination of the participants' age distribution reveals that the majority, 46.0%, fall within the 18–24 age group, followed by 40.6% in the 25–34 age group, and 13.4% in the 35–44 age group. This distribution indicates that the sample is predominantly composed of young individuals, suggesting that food safety and hygiene behavior attitudes are evaluated primarily through the perceptions of younger generations. In terms of gender, 64.4% of the participants are female, while 35.6% are male. This finding shows that female students

demonstrated higher participation in the research process. It also aligns with previous literature suggesting that female individuals may exhibit greater sensitivity toward hygiene and safety-related issues. Regarding the type of high school education, 36.0% of the students graduated from a high school offering culinary or tourism education, whereas 64.0% graduated from other types of high schools. This suggests that the number of participants who received vocational pre-training is relatively lower, and that university-level education may play a more decisive role in shaping knowledge and attitudes in these subject areas.

Table 4. Mean Scores of Responses to Scale Items

<i>Food Safety Scale in University Training Kitchens Items</i>	<i>Mean Score per Item</i>
Food is properly protected during transportation outside the kitchen.	3.6398
The temperature of the cold storage area for food ingredients is visible.	4.0421
Monitoring food temperature can prevent foodborne illnesses.	3.9655
Chafing dishes are properly lit and functional before placing food in them.	3.9579
Food is always placed on ice to maintain proper temperature.	3.8008
Backup items used for buffets are labeled and properly sealed in the kitchen storage.	4.0421
Food that has been left out for a long time is removed from the kitchen.	3.9808
Food in chafing dishes is checked and illuminated.	3.9234
Hot food is always cooked and maintained at the proper temperature.	3.9195
Storage temperatures of ingredients can be monitored.	3.9923
Chafing dishes are cleaned after each use.	3.8927
Attention is paid to avoid wear and chipping on tableware.	3.8582
Chafing dishes are checked before being offered for use.	3.8621
Kitchen equipment is cleaned.	3.9885
The temperatures of hot-holding materials are checked.	4.0383
No handwashing station is available.	3.2644
Hands are washed after every meal service.	3.9080
Reminders are given to wash hands before serving after washing dishes.	3.8812
Water temperature is sufficient for handwashing.	3.8736
Handwashing units are available for operations conducted outside the kitchen.	3.8161
We do not start work in dirty uniforms that would compromise food safety.	3.8352
We tend to eat or drink during kitchen operations.	3.6858
Disposable clean gloves are always worn while preparing food.	3.8314
Hands can be dried on clothing.	3.2605
Wearing jewelry is allowed.	3.0268
We wash our hands after taking a break.	3.9234
We wash our hands after touching our hair or face.	3.9042
<i>Hygiene Behavior Attitude Scale in University Training Kitchens Items</i>	<i>Mean Score per Item</i>
I know the required temperature level in cold storage.	3.9962
I know the required temperature level in dry storage.	3.9119
I know which foods are most susceptible to microbial contamination.	3.9272
I know how long ready-to-serve food can be stored in a refrigerator.	3.9923
I know how frequently cutting boards should be cleaned.	4.0077
I believe different counters should be used to prevent cross-contamination.	4.0000
I care about cleaning utensils (ladles, strainers, spoons, etc.) that fall on the ground.	3.9770
I care about washing my hands after using the restroom in the kitchen.	4.0766
I care about washing my hands before starting work in the kitchen.	4.1034
I care about wearing an apron while working in the kitchen.	3.9540
I care about wearing a hairnet while working in the kitchen.	3.9349
I care about wearing a mask while working in the kitchen.	3.6398
I believe cracked or broken plates and glasses can be used in service.	3.1839
I believe chewing gum is acceptable while preparing food.	3.1801
I believe it is acceptable to touch cooked and ready-to-serve food with bare hands.	3.2337
I believe one can attend school while having the flu or similar illnesses.	3.1877

An examination of participants' responses to the food safety scale shows that, overall, they exhibit a positive attitude. In particular, the high mean scores given to certain items indicate that students pay considerable

attention to food safety rules in university training kitchens. For example, statements such as "The temperature of the cold storage area for food ingredients is visible" ($M = 4.04$), "Backup items used for buffets are labeled and properly sealed in the kitchen storage"

($M = 4.04$), and “The temperatures of hot-holding materials are checked” ($M = 4.03$) were among the highest-rated items. These findings suggest that participants are aware of technical control mechanisms and pay attention to such processes. Likewise, attitudes toward basic hygiene and safety practices were also supported by high average scores, such as “Monitoring food temperature can prevent foodborne illnesses” ($M = 3.97$), “Food that has been left out for a long time is removed from the kitchen” ($M = 3.98$), and “Kitchen equipment is cleaned” ($M = 3.99$). These results indicate that the habits acquired in training kitchens are being internalized in practice. However, certain items with relatively lower average scores are particularly noteworthy. For example, participants’ indecision or agreement with negatively worded statements such as “No handwashing station is available” ($M = 3.26$), “Hands can be dried on clothing” ($M = 3.26$), and “Wearing jewelry is allowed” ($M = 3.03$) indicates that such undesirable hygiene behaviors are not fully rejected. This suggests that some risky habits may still persist. Overall, it was observed that most of the 27 items on the food safety scale had mean scores above 3.80, while only three items had mean scores below 3.30. In this context, the students’ levels of knowledge and attitudes regarding food safety are considered to be high and positive.

Findings related to the hygiene behavior attitude scale indicate that students have a high level of awareness regarding personal cleanliness and hygiene rules. The majority of item means range between 3.90 and 4.10.

Notably high averages were recorded for items such as “I care about washing my hands before starting work” ($M = 4.10$), “I care about washing my hands after using the restroom” ($M = 4.08$), “Cleaning of cutting boards” ($M = 4.01$), and “Storage duration of ready-to-serve food” ($M = 3.99$), which relate to critical hygiene behaviors. This demonstrates that both students’ knowledge levels and behavioral tendencies align well with hygienic practices. In addition, statements such as “Knowledge of cold/dry storage temperatures”, “Awareness of cross-contamination”, and “Use of apron, hairnet, and mask” also received mean scores of 3.90 or higher, indicating that students have largely adopted hygiene rules through both theoretical and practical educational processes. On the other hand, the relatively low average scores for items related to negative and incorrect practices such as “I believe cracked plates can be used in service” ($M = 3.18$), “Chewing gum is acceptable” ($M = 3.18$), “Touching cooked food with bare hands is acceptable” ($M = 3.23$), and “It is acceptable to attend school while sick” ($M = 3.19$) are striking. The fact that these averages are slightly above 3.00 suggests that participants do not clearly reject such negative behaviors, and that some remain undecided or may still lack sufficient knowledge. These items highlight areas that should be prioritized in future educational efforts. In general, the mean scores of this scale are also concentrated around 3.90, leading to the conclusion that students exhibit a high level of awareness regarding hygiene behavior.

Table 5. ANOVA Analysis of Differences in Participants’ Food Safety Perceptions in University Training Kitchens According to Age Groups

Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.		
36.215	2	258	.000		
ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	5.487	2	2.744	3.691	.026
Within Groups	191.756	258	.743		
Total	197.244	260			

To test Hypothesis H2a, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine whether students’ perceptions of food safety significantly differed across age groups. The Levene’s Test for homogeneity of

variances was found to be significant (Levene Statistic = 36.215; $p < .001$), indicating that the assumption of equal variances was violated. Therefore, Dunnett’s C test was used for the post-hoc comparison. According to

the ANOVA results, a statistically significant difference was found among the age groups ($F(2, 258) = 3.691$; $p = .026$). The results of the Dunnett's C post-hoc test revealed that there was a significant difference between the 18–24 and 25–34 age groups. The 18–24 age group showed more positive attitudes and higher

levels of perception regarding food safety. This finding suggests that theoretical and practical training received during the university period may have a stronger impact on raising food safety awareness among younger individuals. Based on these results, Hypothesis H2a was supported.

Table 6. Independent Samples T-Test Analysis of Participants' Food Safety Perceptions in University Training Kitchens by Gender

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
FSMEAN	Male	93	3.9673	.81067	.08406
	Female	168	3.7370	.89445	.06901
Independent Samples Test					
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			T-test for Equality of Means		
FSMEAN	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	4.632	.032	2.059	259	.041

To test Hypothesis H2b, an independent samples t-test was conducted to determine whether participants' perceptions of food safety differed by gender. The Levene's Test for equality of variances indicated that the assumption of equal variances was violated ($F = 4.632$; $p = .032$). Therefore, the t-test results were interpreted based on the unequal variances assumed. According to the analysis results, the mean food safety perception score for male

participants ($M = 3.97$) was found to be higher than that of female participants ($M = 3.74$). This difference was statistically significant ($t(259) = 2.059$; $p = .041$). This finding suggests that male students exhibit more positive attitudes toward food safety in university training kitchens compared to their female counterparts. Based on the statistical results obtained, Hypothesis H2b was supported.

Table 7. Independent Samples T-Test Analysis of Participants' Food Safety Perceptions in University Training Kitchens by Type of High School Education

	HIGHSCHLTYP	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
FSMEAN	Graduate of a High School Offering Culinary or Tourism Education	94	3.3144	1.01067	.10424
	Graduate of a Different Type of High School	167	4.1031	.62495	.04836
Independent Samples Test					
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			T-test for Equality of Means		
FSMEAN	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	101.815	.000	-7.786	259	.000

To test Hypothesis H2c, an independent samples t-test was conducted to determine whether students' perceptions of food safety differed based on the type of high school they graduated from. The result of the Levene's Test was statistically significant ($F = 101.815$; $p < .001$), indicating that the assumption of equal variances was violated. Therefore, the t-test results were interpreted under the assumption of unequal variances. According to the analysis findings, students who graduated from other types of high schools reported a higher mean score in food safety attitude ($M = 4.10$) compared to those who graduated

from high schools offering culinary or tourism education ($M = 3.31$). This difference was highly significant ($t(259) = -7.786$; $p < .001$). This result indicates that students without a vocational high school background exhibit more positive attitudes toward food safety. The finding may raise questions regarding the quality or intensity of vocational high school training. It may also suggest that university-level education is more influential in shaping food safety attitudes among students without prior vocational preparation. In light of these findings, Hypothesis H2c was strongly supported.

Table 8. ANOVA Analysis of Differences in Participants' Hygiene Behavior Attitudes in University Training Kitchens According to Age Groups

Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.		
30.693	2	258	.000		
ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.592	2	.796	1.057	.349
Within Groups	194.344	258	.753		
Total	197.244	260			

To test Hypothesis H3a, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine whether participants' levels of hygiene behavior attitudes differed across age groups. The Levene's Test for homogeneity of variances was found to be significant ($F = 30.693$; $p < .001$), indicating that the variances between groups were not equal. Despite this, the ANOVA analysis revealed no statistically significant difference in hygiene behavior

attitudes among the different age groups ($F(2, 258) = 1.057$; $p = .349$). This result suggests that students' attitudes toward hygiene behavior do not vary significantly by age, and that no meaningful difference exists among the age groups in this regard. It can be inferred that awareness of hygiene practices is more likely shaped by educational or personal experiences, rather than by age alone. Based on the findings, Hypothesis H3a was rejected.

Table 9. Independent Samples T-Test Analysis of Participants' Hygiene Behavior Attitudes in University Training Kitchens by Gender

HATTMEAN	GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
	Male	93	3.8817	.79983	.08294
Female	168	3.7068	.89993	.06943	
Independent Samples Test					
HATTMEAN	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		T-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	3.728	.055	1.563	259	.119

To test Hypothesis H3b, an independent samples t-test was conducted to examine whether students' levels of hygiene behavior attitudes differed significantly by gender. The Levene's Test result ($F = 3.728$; $p = .055$) was near the threshold of significance, suggesting a borderline violation of the assumption of equal variances; thus, the t-test was interpreted accordingly. According to the results, the

mean hygiene behavior attitude score of male participants ($M = 3.88$) was higher than that of female participants ($M = 3.71$); however, this difference was not statistically significant ($t(259) = 1.563$; $p = .119$). This finding indicates that attitudes toward hygiene behavior are not significantly influenced by gender. Therefore, based on the results obtained, Hypothesis H3b was rejected.

Table 7. Independent Samples T-Test Analysis of Participants' Food Safety Perceptions in University Training Kitchens by Type of High School Education

HATTMEAN	HIGHSCHLTYP	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
	Graduate of a High School Offering Culinary or Tourism Education	94	3.2201	.95430	.09843
Graduate of a Different Type of High School	167	4.0782	.63507	.04914	
Independent Samples Test					
HATTMEAN	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		T-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	66.169	.000	-8.698	259	.000

To test Hypothesis H3c, an independent samples t-test was conducted to determine whether students' hygiene behavior attitudes differed according to the type of high school they graduated from. The Levene's Test result was statistically significant ($F = 66.169$; $p < .001$), indicating that the assumption of equal variances was violated. Therefore, the t-test results were interpreted under the unequal variances assumed condition. According to the analysis, the mean hygiene behavior attitude score of students who graduated from high schools offering culinary or tourism education was 3.22, while the mean score for those from other types of high schools was 4.08. This difference was found to be highly significant ($t(259) = -8.698$; $p < .001$). This finding reveals a statistically significant difference in students' hygiene behavior attitudes based on the type of high school education. Notably, the relatively lower attitude scores of students from vocational high schools are striking. This may indicate that hygiene practices are not sufficiently emphasized during vocational training, or that students may not fully internalize the intended learning outcomes during that process. On the other hand, the more positive attitudes displayed by students without a vocational background but who received university-level training in professional kitchens suggest that higher education may have a transformative effect on hygiene awareness. In vocational high schools, students' intrinsic motivation may still be relatively low and topics that require a high level of discipline, such as hygiene attitudes, may not receive adequate attention. Moreover, food hygiene standards and practical guidelines may be less rigorously supervised in these institutions. Based on these findings, Hypothesis H3c was strongly supported.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study reveals significant findings by examining the food safety and hygiene behavior attitudes of students receiving training in university practice kitchens in light of demographic variables. Overall, it was determined that students' attitudes toward both food safety and hygiene behavior were positive. This indicates that both theoretical and practical education at the university level are effective in improving students' awareness

and attitudes.

Gündüz and Aydoğan (2015), in their study measuring associate degree students' awareness of food safety, found a significant relationship between age and food safety awareness, but no statistically significant difference between gender and food safety. Açıkalin (2019) evaluated university students' knowledge and attitudes toward food safety and concluded that there was no significant relationship between food safety knowledge or attitudes and gender or age. Similarly, Özcan (2020), in a study conducted on culinary and gastronomy students, found no significant difference in knowledge levels regarding hygiene and food safety based on gender. In light of the results of the present study, however, it was concluded that food safety attitudes showed significant differences according to age and gender. At this point, the findings diverge from previous studies. In particular, the higher awareness of food safety among younger individuals highlights the impact of university education. Furthermore, the fact that male students displayed more positive attitudes compared to female students indicates the role of gender in shaping behaviors and attitudes.

In terms of high school background, it was found that students without a vocational high school education exhibited more positive food safety attitudes, bringing forward important implications regarding the quality and content of pre-vocational education. When hygiene behavior attitudes were examined, the findings can be summarized as follows: age and gender variables did not lead to significant differences, whereas significant differences were observed according to high school type. The lower hygiene attitudes of vocational high school graduates point to either inadequacies in the inclusion of hygiene practices within vocational training programs or students' inability to fully internalize the expected behaviors during this process. Aratoğlu (2015), in a study covering students receiving culinary and nutrition training at Mengen Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School and Mengen Vocational School, examined their knowledge and practice levels on food safety and hygiene, and identified significant differences among the student groups. Accordingly, the food safety

and hygiene knowledge levels of students at Mengen Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School were lower compared to those of vocational school students. These findings support the results of the present study. Based on this, it can be argued that education at the university level has the potential to positively transform food safety and hygiene awareness.

The results of this research highlight the need to examine the content and quality of vocational education in the field of food safety and hygiene behavior. It is important that universities develop not only theoretical knowledge but also training programs in practice kitchens to incorporate current hygiene standards. Moreover, designing comprehensive training programs that target all students, regardless of demographic differences such as gender and age, may contribute to strengthening these attitudes further.

It is recommended that educational institutions operating in the fields of gastronomy and tourism revise their vocational training curricula to place greater emphasis on hygiene and food safety. In this regard, expanding opportunities for practical training, promoting certifications, and organizing regular awareness seminars could be beneficial. University curricula should strengthen both theoretical and practical training in food safety and hygiene, align content with standards and implement regular monitoring of practical practices. In vocational high schools, hygiene education should be enhanced with more hands-on training and regular supervision, while initiatives to increase students' motivation and awareness can reinforce positive behaviors. For future academic research, including samples from different universities is suggested to enhance the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, a detailed examination of psychosocial factors, educational tendencies, and cultural variables affecting students' attitudes and behaviors could enrich the field and help identify necessary measures. In the food industry, mandatory training for interns and employees, consistent monitoring and collaboration with universities can support proper hygiene practices in real-world settings. In conclusion, this study represents an

important step toward understanding the relationship between demographic variables and attitudes toward food safety and hygiene behavior in university practice kitchens. At the same time, it emphasizes the necessity of continuous improvement in educational processes and the strengthening of sectoral collaborations.

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